

1 Designing Fe₃O₄ Nanocubes for Intracellular
2 Magnetic Hyperthermia: Unraveling the Role of Fe²⁺
3 Deficiencies, FeO Sub-Domains, and Structural
4 Defects

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3 ABSTRACT

4 Herein, by studying a stepwise phase transformation of 23 nm FeO-Fe₃O₄ core-shell nanocubes
5 into Fe₃O₄, we identify a composition at which the magnetic heating performance of the nanocubes
6 is not affected by the medium viscosity and aggregation. Structural and magnetic characterizations
7 reveal the transformation of the FeO-Fe₃O₄ nanocubes from having stoichiometric phase
8 compositions into Fe²⁺ deficient Fe₃O₄ phases. The resultant nanocubes contain tiny compressed
9 and randomly distributed FeO sub-domains as well as structural defects. This phase transformation
10 causes a tenfold increase in the magnetic heating of the nanocubes, which remains exceptionally
11 insensitive to the medium viscosity as well as aggregation unlike similarly sized single-phase
12 magnetite nanocubes. We observe that the dominant relaxation mechanism switches from Néel in
13 fresh core-shell nanocubes to Brownian in partially oxidized nanocubes and once again to Néel in
14 completely treated nanocubes. The Fe²⁺ deficiencies and structural defects appear to reduce the
15 magnetic energy barrier and anisotropy field, thereby driving the overall relaxation into Néel
16 process. The magnetic heating of the particles remains unchanged through a progressive
17 internalization/association to ovarian cancer cells. Moreover, the particles induce a significant cell
18 death after being exposed to hyperthermia treatment. Here, we present the largest heating
19 performance that has been reported to date for 23 nm iron oxide nanoparticles under cellular and
20 intracellular conditions. Our findings clearly demonstrate the positive impacts of the Fe²⁺
21 deficiencies and structural defects in the Fe₃O₄ structure on the heating performance under cellular
22 and intracellular conditions.

1 Anisotropically shaped magnetic nanoparticles have attracted great attention in the last few years
2 especially with regard to magnetic hyperthermia (MH) and magnetic particle imaging (MPI)
3 applications.¹⁻⁴ Magnetic nanoparticle mediated MH is an emerging therapeutic approach which
4 induces cancer cell death through heat damage, which has succeeded in retreating brain tumors in
5 clinical trials.^{5,6} Iron oxide based nanoparticles are an indispensable candidate for MH due to their
6 biocompatibility (*i.e.* they are FDA approved) and biodegradability.⁷ There has been significant
7 progress in controlled syntheses of spherical, cubic, star-, and octapod-shaped iron oxide
8 nanoparticles thanks to advancements in the thermal decomposition of organometallic
9 precursors.⁸⁻¹⁶ Over the last few years, a fairly good understanding of how the particle's
10 morphological features depend on the synthesis conditions has been also acquired.

11 The thermal decomposition of iron-oleate, pioneered by Hyeon et al.,⁸ is one of the most studied
12 synthesis procedures due to its versatility and scalability. The biggest drawback of this synthesis
13 is the formation of antiferromagnetic (AFM) FeO-ferrimagnetic (FiM) Fe₃O₄ core-shell (CS)
14 particles caused by the reductive chemistry of the decomposition reaction.¹⁷⁻²⁴ Such core-shell
15 nanoparticles, synthesized using iron-oleate²⁵ or other iron precursors,²⁶ have been characterized
16 by varieties of advanced methods. It is known that the FeO phase deteriorates the overall
17 magnetization of the particles, thus jeopardizing their hyperthermia efficacy. There have been
18 handful of studies on resolving the issue by attempting to directly fabricate single Fe₃O₄ phase
19 particles.^{27,28} Recently, Chen et al.²⁹ have modified the iron-oleate decomposition pathway by
20 adding aromatic ethers as co-solvents and synthesized single phase ferrimagnetic spherical
21 nanoparticles. Unni et al.³⁰ have shown that, by adding molecular oxygen to the reaction's
22 protective gas during the decomposition reaction, semi-spherical single phase iron oxide
23 nanoparticles can be formed. Alternatively, other studies have also shown post-synthesis

1 oxidations of the FeO-Fe₃O₄ CS particles,¹¹ mostly at elevated temperatures in organic media.³¹ It
2 has been shown that structural defects like anti-phase boundaries in as-prepared and annealed
3 particles form small domain-like regions, which account for the reduction in both the magnetic
4 moment and the heating performances.^{20,32}

5 An equally crucial feature of magnetic nanoparticles for use in intracellular hyperthermia is that
6 they need to generate sufficient heat in the cellular space, regardless of whether they are immobile
7 (intracellular viscosity $\eta=50-140$ mPa·s)³³ or clustered within endosomes. Recent studies have
8 shown that the magnetic heating of particles strongly depends on their environment *e.g.* the
9 immobilization and clustering and will be dramatically reduced (up to 90%) depending on the
10 particle size, chemical composition, and aggregation inside the live cells.³⁴⁻³⁸ Cabrera et al.³⁹ have
11 exploited alternating-current (AC) hysteresis loop measurements to demonstrate that 24 nm
12 magnetite nanocubes lose their high specific absorption rate (SAR) nearly entirely when dispersed
13 in viscous media (~ 100 mPa·s). Theoretical studies have also described how the viscosity
14 influences the magnetic heat dissipation of nanoparticles.³⁹⁻⁴¹ It would appear that magnetic
15 nanoparticles with a perfect crystal structure and high magnetic anisotropy, thus relaxing via the
16 Brownian mechanism, do not adequately fulfill intracellular hyperthermia requirements. In an
17 attempt to overcome the intracellular heating issue, 15 nm aminosilane-coated iron oxide
18 nanoparticles have been clinically used.⁴² Although 15 nm nanoparticles are less dependent on the
19 medium viscosity, they generate considerably less magnetic heat than bigger nanoparticles.^{39,42,43}

20 Thus far, despite being a highly relevant criterion, very few studies have been dedicated to
21 engineering the magnetic relaxation mechanisms of iron oxide nanocubes in order to fabricate heat
22 mediators, which generate large heat and concomitantly preserve it inside the cells. Moreover, the
23 fact that the magnetic nanoparticles that are utilized in intracellular MH and MPI experiments

1 share the same nanomagnetism principles highlights the importance of designing novel magnetic
2 nanoparticles as MPI/MH theranostic agents.^{4,34,44} To this end, nanoparticles should be fabricated
3 so that they can efficiently maintain the heating capacity in the intracellular environment. To date,
4 there have not been any reports on such a particle system that can accomplish this. This poses an
5 intriguing question: *could compositional deficiencies and structural defects in the particles favor*
6 *their heating capacity in biological matrices?*

7 In this study, we tackle this specific question by performing a stepwise thermal treatment and phase
8 transformation of 23 nm FeO-Fe₃O₄ CS nanocubes. The nanocubes transform from a CS structure
9 to an Fe²⁺ deficient Fe₃O₄ phase, which have compressed FeO sub-domains and defects, through
10 the thermal process. The SAR of the nanocubes increases significantly, yet it remains insensitive
11 to the medium viscosity, clustering, and internalization to cells, unlike similarly sized iron oxide
12 nanocubes that are produced *via* direct methods. Our findings demonstrate that the Fe²⁺
13 deficiencies and structural defects drive the overall relaxation to Néel rather than Brownian and
14 hence favor the heating performance of the nanocubes in cellular or viscous environments.

15 Highly uniform FeO-Fe₃O₄ CS nanocubes with an edge length of 23 nm were synthesized by
16 thermal decomposition of iron-oleate (Figure S1, refer to the electronic supporting information
17 (ESI)).^{8,18} The nanocubes were thermally treated at 80°C for set time intervals after being coated
18 with polyethylene glycol (PEG) derivative polymers and being transferred into water (ESI, Scheme
19 1, and Table 1). Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements confirm that the particle's
20 hydrodynamic size remains unchanged throughout the entire thermal treatment process in water
21 (Figure S3, ESI). The magnetic heating performance of the particles, which was evaluated with
22 the calorimetric measure of the SAR quantity, increases significantly as the particles are thermally
23 treated. The SAR, measured at 301 kHz and 24 kA/m, soars from 15 to 382 W/g_{Fe} upon 48 h of

1 treatment (Figure 1a, a typical calorimetric SAR measurement is plotted in Figure S4). The SAR
 2 values obtained for aliquots taken at intermediate time intervals increase stepwise, suggesting a
 3 gradual shrinkage of the FeO and an enlargement of the Fe₃O₄ domains, respectively, as a result
 4 of a longer thermal treatment. The observed improvements are to be expected since the FeO phase
 5 is paramagnetic at room temperature and therefore it scarcely contributes to the magnetic heating
 6 (Scheme 1).

7 **Scheme 1.** Evolution of the structural, compositional, and magnetic configurations of the
 8 nanocubes through the thermal treatment process. The different spin colors indicate differently
 9 oriented domain-like regions.

11 To elucidate the governing magnetic relaxation mechanism at each oxidation stage, we first
 12 performed SAR measurements at different medium viscosities (η) and matched these results with
 13 the results of the ac-susceptibility measurements. These measurements enabled us to distinguish
 14 the Néel relaxation, which occurs when internal magnetic spins rotate from the Brownian
 15 relaxation which, in turn occurs through the rotation of the whole particle. The particles were
 16 dispersed in 58.5:41.5 wt%, 27.2:72.8 wt%, and 15.7:84.3 wt% water-glycerol mixtures,

1 corresponding to a mean η of 3.8, 23.0, 97.3 mPa·s.³⁹ Remarkably, the IO23/48 sample shows only
2 a 15 to 18% drop in the SAR value at 301 and 100 kHz, respectively, when the viscosity increases
3 by nearly two orders of magnitude, whereas the drop in the SAR value in the intermediate IO23/24
4 sample is significantly larger despite having a smaller magnetic volume V_m (Figure 1b). These
5 results demonstrate that the IO23/48 nanocubes relax more dominantly *via* the Néel mechanism
6 than the intermediately treated nanocubes. Note that the time constant τ_N depends exponentially
7 on both the anisotropy constant K and the particle magnetic volume V_m (Eq. S10), and is
8 independent of η . This seems counterintuitive to one's expectation, implying that particles with a
9 larger V_m relax predominantly *via* the Brownian mechanism, in which the time constant τ_B depends
10 linearly on both η and the particle hydrodynamic volume V_h (Eq. S9), therefore responding more
11 drastically to η . The promising viscosity-independent magnetic heating performance of the
12 IO23/48 sample is remarkable considering there is nearly a 100% SAR drop over a similar
13 viscosity range for 24 nm magnetite nanocubes that are synthesized *via* a different heat-up
14 protocol.³⁹ The findings suggest that the relaxation mechanism of the nanocubes is governed by
15 other structural features, not just by the apparent physical sizes, which despite their subtlety are
16 decisive.

17 To further verify the SAR results by applying magnetic measurements, AC hysteresis loops were
18 recorded at 200 kHz for the IO23/48 nanocubes that were dispersed in similar water-glycerol
19 mixtures. No significant changes in the hysteresis loop area (A) were observed when η was
20 increased by two orders of magnitude, confirming that the SAR (*i.e.* proportional to $A \times f$)⁴⁵ is
21 marginally dependent on the particle immobilization (Figures 1c and S5). The viscosity effect,
22 however, became more significant when lower field intensities were applied (Figure S6), which is
23 in agreement with recent findings.³⁹

1 The effect of particle clustering on the heating efficiency was further probed by increasing the
 2 particle's hydrodynamic size by adding BSA protein to the dispersion and recording the AC loops
 3 at 100 kHz (Figure 1d, Table S1). The hysteresis loop area A of the IO23/48 nanocubes drops
 4 merely by 34% when d_h increases from 74 to 114 nm, but it remains virtually constant for 810 nm
 5 clusters (Figure S5). Although the IO23/48 nanocubes reveal slightly higher aggregation effects
 6 on the SAR than the 20 nm maghemite nanoparticles reported by Ovejero et al.,⁴⁶ it is significant
 7 to highlight that the SAR of the IO23/48 in the aggregated state is two times higher than that of
 8 maghemite nanoparticles. The stronger aggregation effect is likely attributed to the larger core size
 9 of the IO23/48 nanocubes, which results into stronger intra-aggregate magnetic dipolar
 10 interactions. The maximum magnetization (M_{max}) and remanence magnetization (M_r) reduce by
 11 20% as bigger clusters are formed. This indicates that the intra-aggregate dipole-dipole interactions
 12 lead to demagnetizing configurations in the clusters.

13 **Table 1.** Sample names, treatment conditions, edge length (L_c), number-weighted hydrodynamic
 14 diameter (d_h), polydispersity index (PDI), lattice constants (a_{RS} and a_S), and weight fraction of
 15 FeO and Fe₃O₄ phases extracted from TEM, DLS, and Rietveld analyses, respectively.

name	L_c (nm)	time(h)/temp.(°C)	d_h (nm)/PDI	$a_{RS}/a_S(\text{Å})$	FeO/Fe ₃ O ₄ (wt%)
IO23/0	23	0/---	43(3)/0.17	4.270(5)/8.432(5)	53(3)/47(3)
IO23/3	23	3/80	40(1)/0.14	4.259(5)/8.420(5)	36(3)/64(3)
IO23/6	23	6/80	40(2)/0.15	4.259(5)/8.410(5)	29(3)/71(3)
IO23/24	23	24/80	41(3)/0.14	---/8.390(3)	0/100
IO23/48	23	48/80	45(3)/0.19	---/8.385(3)	0/100

16

1
 2 **Figure 1.** (a) Field dependence of the specific absorption rate (SAR) of 23 nm nanocubes that
 3 underwent the thermal treatment for different time intervals, measured at 301 kHz. (b) SAR
 4 evolution vs. glycerol content (wt%) and η , measured at 24 kA/m and 301, 200, and 100 kHz for
 5 IO23/48 and 301 kHz for IO23/24 nanocubes. (c) Effect of the medium viscosity η and (d) the
 6 particle cluster hydrodynamic size d_h on AC hysteresis loops of IO23/48 nanocubes, recorded at
 7 200 and 100 kHz, respectively. The samples' characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

8 Complex ac-susceptibility (ACS) measurements were then carried out on all the samples in water
 9 and in water-glycerol mixtures in order to probe their magnetic relaxation mechanisms as well as
 10 their dependence on η . The imaginary part χ'' of the as-prepared CS nanocubes IO23/0 shows an
 11 appreciable double peak spectrum (marked with arrows in Figure 2a). The peak positioned at *ca.*

1 3 kHz can be unambiguously attributed to the Brownian relaxation, whereas the broad hump at
2 *ca.* 150 kHz is assigned to the Néel relaxation (Figure 2a). This means that in the IO23/0 sample
3 $\tau_N < \tau_B$, and thus the Néel relaxation dominates. After 3 and 6 h of thermal treatment, the χ'' peak
4 becomes symmetric and has no high frequency shoulder, indicating the domination of the
5 Brownian process (i.e. $\tau_N > \tau_B$) in the IO23/3 and IO23/6 samples (Figure 2a). Remarkably, the
6 χ'' peak becomes asymmetric towards high frequency regimes in the IO23/48 sample, indicating
7 that $\tau_N < \tau_B$ and hence the Néel process contributes more significantly to the effective relaxation.
8 The Néel shoulder can be easily appreciated by observing a pronounced double peak spectrum
9 when the particles are dispersed in $\eta=97$ mPa·s (Figure 2b, green markers) wherein the Brownian
10 and Néel relaxation frequencies are well separated. The peak assignment can be further confirmed
11 by looking at the ACS spectra that were recorded at different viscosities (Figure 2b). The peak at
12 3 kHz moves gradually towards lower frequencies as η increases, as is to be expected for the
13 Brownian relaxation. The hump at 150 kHz preserves its position, which is an intrinsic nature of
14 the Néel relaxation.

15 These results suggest that there are intermediate structures (i.e. IO23/6) which behave in a more
16 magnetically blocked manner than the IO23/48 nanocubes. This is an intriguing phenomenon
17 which has not yet been reported. These findings fully support the viscosity dependent SAR
18 behavior wherein a higher SAR drop was detected for the IO23/24. Remarkably, the viscosities
19 estimated from the fits to the χ'' spectra (see Eq. S8, Figure 2b) match well with the values
20 measured using a rheometer (Figure S7, ESI). This confirms the credibility of the applied model.

21 These phenomena are quantitatively reflected in the magnetic energy barrier quantity KV_m which
22 is derived from modelling the ACS spectra using the modified Debye model (Eq. S5, Figure S8,
23 ESI). Interestingly, KV_m rises from the IO23/0 sample to the IO23/3 and IO23/6 samples,

1 indicating a switch in the dominant relaxation mechanism from the Néel to the Brownian
 2 mechanism during the initial oxidation stages (Figure S8). We hypothesize that the Fe₃O₄ domains
 3 grow towards the core more easily along disordered boundaries and defects, as they offer a higher
 4 ion diffusion rate. This could plausibly lead to the formation of a mosaic crystal structure with
 5 small FeO grains (Scheme 1) rather than a perfect planar growth of the FeO-Fe₃O₄ interface
 6 towards the core. The Fe₃O₄ domains that formed during the initial stages appear to possess a
 7 short-range cation/magnetic ordering and K quantity, which is closer to the bulk magnetite *i.e.* 11-
 8 13 kJ/m³.³¹ This leads to the domination of the Brownian mechanism in the IO23/6 particles. The
 9 KV_m decreases as the oxidation proceeds further, which is a strong indication of a larger
 10 contribution of the Néel mechanism to the effective relaxation. These trends were also reflected in
 11 the SAR *vs.* H plots (Figure S9). Noticeably, the SAR already saturates at $H=20$ kA/m for the
 12 IO23/48 sample, whereas it keeps rising linearly for the IO23/6 sample. These results indicate that
 13 there is a lower anisotropy field (H_A , given by $H_A=2K/M_s$) and K for the IO23/48 sample than for
 14 the IO23/6 one.

15 **Figure 2.** (a) Real (dashed lines) χ' and imaginary (markers) χ'' parts of complex ac-susceptibility
 16 spectra measured on IO23 sample series in water, and (b) on IO23/48 samples in different
 17

1 viscosities (*i.e.* water-glycerol mixtures). The solid black lines are the best fits to χ'' using Eq. S5
2 and S8.

3 Additional insight was acquired by investigating the crystal structure of the particles using high
4 angle annular dark field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM). The
5 intensity difference observed in the high resolution HAADF-STEM image (Figure 3a) suggests
6 that the IO23/0 nanocubes have a CS structure. The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) pattern acquired
7 from the middle of the particle can be indexed to the [100] zone axis of FeO. Instead, the FFT
8 pattern obtained near the edge can be indexed to the [100] zone of either magnetite (Fe₃O₄) or
9 maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃). The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the IO23/0 confirms the presence
10 of both crystalline FeO and Fe₃O₄ phases (Figure 3b). The reflection positions coincide with
11 Fe_{0.942}O (ICSD: 98-002-4696, Rock-salt (RS)) and Fe_{2.96}O₄ (ICSD: 98-008-2443, Inverse spinel
12 (S)), with a FeO:Fe₃O₄ phase ratio of 53:47 wt% based on the Rietveld analysis (Table 1, Table
13 S3, and ESI).

14 The fine structure of monochromated electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) is used to
15 differentiate between Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ valency, which enables us to distinguish between maghemite
16 and magnetite. Based on the EELS maps, the core of the as prepared IO23/0 sample contains
17 88.9±6.2% Fe²⁺ (Figure S10, ESI). The small amount of Fe³⁺ detected at the core most likely
18 originates from the shell on top and underneath. Near the edge of the nanoparticle, the shell
19 contains twice as much Fe³⁺ (62.1±6.4%) as Fe²⁺, which is characteristic of the Fe₃O₄ phase. These
20 findings indicate that the IO23/0 nanocubes have a CS structure with sharp AFM-FiM interfaces.

21 A gradual evolution of the nanocubes from a biphasic system to a nearly single spinel phase after
22 48 h of thermal treatment can be seen by comparing the XRD patterns (Figure 3b), which were
23 recorded at different time intervals (see Table 1 for a quantitative phase analysis). The FFT analysis

1 of the high resolution HAADF-STEM image of the IO23/48 sample (Figure 3c) reveals the
2 disappearance of the CS structure. Nevertheless, it was possible to detect relatively small FeO sub-
3 domains which had not been observed in the XRD pattern. These domains are randomly distributed
4 throughout the entire particle, even on the shell (green rectangular in Figure 3c). Anti-phase
5 boundary defects are also expected in these particles as they survive even higher annealing
6 temperatures.^{20,47}

7 From the Rietveld analyses of the XRD patterns, we have discerned that the lattice constants of
8 FeO (a_{RS} , 4.270 Å) and Fe₃O₄ (a_S , 8.432 Å) in the IO23/0 sample decrease when the treatment time
9 is prolonged, which is visually apparent through a shift in the reflection positions towards higher
10 angles (*e.g.* (311)_S, (400)_S, and (200)_{RS} reflections). A similar trend has been reported for a
11 comparable system²⁰ and Co_xFe_{1-x}O/Co_xFe_{3-x}O₄ nanoparticles.⁴⁸ A decrease in a_S with respect to
12 the nominal bulk value of magnetite is expected for Fe₃O₄, which indicates the release of the lattice
13 expansion. The drop in the FeO lattice constant is, however, unexpected and suggests an
14 accumulation of pressure on the FeO sub-domains as the oxidation progresses. This is presumably
15 caused by the Fe₃O₄ domains which grow throughout the particles.⁴⁷ The GPa pressure range on
16 the FeO domains substantially hampers the diffusion of Fe²⁺ towards outer layers, leading to the
17 survival and migration of the FeO domains through the particles (Scheme 1).²⁰ According to the
18 EELS valency maps (Figures 3d and 3e), the IO23/48 particles consist mainly of Fe³⁺ (84.4±7.1%),
19 with some leftover Fe²⁺ (*ca.* 16%). Compared with the nominal Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ ratio in magnetite (*i.e.*
20 66% versus 34%), this result suggests *ca.* 18% Fe²⁺ deficiencies.

21 Tilt series of HAADF-STEM images of the nanocubes were used as an input for a 3D
22 reconstruction. It then became clear that the IO23/0 particles have a cubic shape with a smooth
23 surface (Figure 3f). After the full thermal treatment, the morphology of the particle surface is more

1 rough (Figure 3g). It is known that nanoparticles that have a reduced valency, *e.g.* FeO and $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x}\text{O}$, become bigger when they are oxidized due to the adsorption of a considerable amount of
 2 oxygen.⁴⁸ The formation of small hills and valleys on the particle surface may be an indication of
 3 particle growth. The shape of the IO23/48 nanocubes falls between a perfect cube and a sphere as
 4 a result of the surface roughness and rounded edges. This leads to the reduction of shape anisotropy
 5 and eventually the effective K and H_A quantities, driving the dominating spin relaxation to the Néel
 6 process and favoring the heating in viscous environments.
 7

8
 9 **Figure 3.** (a) High resolution HAADF-STEM image of as-prepared (IO23/0) particles: insets are
 10 Fourier analysis diffraction patterns of regions containing FeO and magnetite/maghemite. (b) X-

1 ray diffraction patterns of all the samples: (1) IO23/0, (2) IO23/3, (3) IO23/6, (4) IO23/24, and (5)
2 IO23/48. (c) High resolution HAADF-STEM image of the IO23/48 particles: insets are Fourier
3 analysis diffraction patterns of regions containing FeO and magnetite/maghemite. (d) Fe⁺² and (e)
4 Fe⁺³ valency maps obtained by fitting the EELS spectra in each pixel to the reference spectra. (f)
5 and (g) 3D visualizations of individual IO23/0 and IO23/48 nanocubes, respectively, which were
6 reconstructed using electron tomography. Darker spots in the HAADF-STEM image (c) are due
7 to a relatively long exposure time to the high energy electron beam.

8 ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer spectroscopy (MS) was performed in order to differentiate between the magnetite
9 and maghemite phases⁴⁹ and to study the magnetization dynamics of the IO23/48 particles. The
10 shape of the 300 K spectrum, having more weight to the outer lines at the positive velocity side,
11 clearly indicates the presence of Fe₃O₄ (Figure 4a).^{50,51} It was possible to fit all MS spectra with a
12 superposition of three magnetic hyperfine patterns. Two 6-line patterns (#1 and #2) are dominant,
13 showing a distribution (assumed Gaussian) of static magnetic hyperfine fields. A weaker third one
14 (#3) is better approached assuming a relaxation pattern due to dynamical fluctuations of the
15 hyperfine field, as it is expected for nanoparticles (refer to Table 2).

16 First, we concentrate on the contributions from the static patterns. Both the center shifts (S) and
17 the relative spectral areas (RA) of the 300 K spectrum are well consistent with magnetite.
18 Subspectra #1 and #2 correspond to the Fe³⁺ in the tetrahedral A sites and the Fe^{2.5+} in the
19 octahedral B sites due to the fast electron hopping between Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ at this temperature. The
20 area ratio of RA (#1) and RA (#2) is 0.6(1) (the ideal one would be 0.5), indicating that there are
21 Fe²⁺ deficiencies in octahedral sites. Upon lowering temperature the area ratio changes as the
22 electron hopping slows down. This results in the presence of Fe³⁺ in both the A and B sites, and
23 Fe²⁺ in the B sites. In bulk magnetite this is connected to a well-defined phase transition, the

1 Verwey transition, from cubic to monoclinic around 120 K.⁵² Mössbauer spectra of magnetite
2 nanoparticles with sizes comparable to ours have shown that the transition may occur continuously
3 over a wide range of temperatures, caused by fractal-like granular assemblies originated from the
4 synthesis.⁵¹ At lower temperatures, even a well crystallized magnetite reveals a complex pattern
5 due to the presence of Fe³⁺ (A), Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ in the distorted B sites. However, based on our MS
6 spectra at 20 K, no distinctions can be made among the various octahedral sites. Despite this,
7 subspectra #1 and #2 can be assigned to Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ with a spectral area ratio of 2.3(2) based on
8 the center shifts. This diverges from the ideal ratio of 2 in magnetite, once more indicating that
9 there are some Fe²⁺ deficiencies.

10 For all temperatures, we find an additional spectrum (#3) that is attributed to some trivalent iron
11 ions, which are subjected to magnetic moment fluctuations. For the fitting, we have used a standard
12 2-level relaxation process without exchange splitting.⁵³ Moment fluctuation rates are in the order
13 of 100 MHz. A close-lying origin of this contribution could be iron on the surface layers of
14 particles. While the spectral area of #3 amounts to about 10% at low temperatures, it increases to
15 about 30% of the total spectral area at 300 K. The increase is mainly due to approaching the
16 superparamagnetic blocking temperature of the particles' ensemble. Furthermore, we have found
17 no resolved spectral contribution of FeO, which typically shows two doublets with divalent isomer
18 shifts of *ca.* 1 mm/s⁵⁴ that should become clearly visible at 300 K (when FeO is in its paramagnetic
19 state). Further discussions on the superparamagnetic behavior of the nanocubes can be found in
20 the ESI.

21 A remarkable feature of zero-field-cooled (ZFC) curves is the appearance of a sharp Verwey
22 transition hump upon annealing for 6 h (IO23/6) (Figure 4b and S11). The transition peak does not
23 exist in the IO23/0 sample and becomes more pronounced from the IO23/3 sample to the IO23/6

1 sample. The transition occurs at *ca.* 120 K in these nanocubes, which perfectly matches the
2 transition temperature of bulk Fe₃O₄, *i.e.* 121 K.⁵² Noticeably, the Verwey hump disappears in the
3 IO23/48 sample as if the transition happens over a wide temperature range, in agreement with the
4 previous findings from Mössbauer spectroscopy.⁵¹ This phenomenon could be related to some Fe²⁺
5 deficiencies, a short-range cation disorder and a spin disorder. It is also known that off-
6 stoichiometric magnetite nanoparticles do not reveal a sudden rise in M around the transition
7 temperature.^{29,52} The Fe²⁺ deficiencies, remaining FeO sub-domains, and structural defects distort
8 the magnetic domain coherency and presumably results in the reduction of KV_m and H_A . These
9 features drive the overall relaxation to the Néel rather than the Brownian. Temperature dependent
10 AC susceptibility spectra recorded at different excitation frequencies reveal interesting features
11 such as a pronounced χ'' kink at *ca.* 300 K (Figure 4c). This kink could be related to the blocking
12 temperature T_B of the Fe₃O₄ domains, which are separated by tiny FeO domains and/or anti-phase
13 boundaries. Moreover, there seems to be another χ'' peak at temperatures higher than 400 K, which
14 can be attributed to an increase in the T_B due to inter-particle dipole-dipole interactions⁵⁵ and/or
15 the collective behavior of the Fe₃O₄ domains within a single nanocube.

1
2 **Figure 4.** (a) ^{57}Fe Mössbauer absorption spectra of IO23/48 recorded at different temperatures.
3 The red lines are the best fits to experimental data composed of a superposition of various
4 subspectral components (#1, #2, #3). (b) Temperature dependent zero-field-cooled ZFC
5 magnetization curves of IO23 sample series recorded at 5 mT warming-cooling fields. (c)
6 Temperature dependent imaginary parts χ'' of the susceptibility measured at various excitation
7 frequencies ω . (d) M - H loops recorded at 298 K, and (e) M_s values estimated from the fits to the
8 M - H curves and the exchange bias fields H_E which were derived from FC hysteresis loops at 10 K.

9 **Table 2:** Hyperfine parameters of ^{57}Fe the Fe Mössbauer spectra of the IO23/48 sample recorded at
10 different temperatures.

T (K)	subspectrum	S (mm/s)	B (T)	σ (T)	RA(%)
20	#1	0.34(1)	51.3(2)	1.2(2)	62(2)
20	#2	0.74(1)	51.4(2)	1.7(2)	27(2)
20	#3	0.2(1)	50*		11(3)
80	#1	0.39(1)	50.9(2)	1.3(2)	61(2)
80	#2	0.71(1)	48.5(2)	3.7(2)	32(2)

80	#3	0.2(1)	50*		7(3)
120	#1	0.36(1)	50.6(2)	1.0(2)	51(2)
120	#2	0.66(1)	48.3(2)	2.9(2)	39(2)
120	#3	0.2(1)	50*		11(3)
300	#1	0.24(1)	47.4(2)	1.1(2)	27(2)
300	#2	0.52(1)	44.2(2)	2.6(2)	44(2)
300	#3	0.1(2)	40*		29(3)

1 T: absorber temperature; S: center shift relative to α -Fe at room temperature; B: magnetic
2 hyperfine field; σ : width of Gaussian distribution of B ; RA: relative spectral area contribution; *:
3 fixed parameter, 2-level relaxation pattern (ref. to the main text)

4 The magnetization M increases abruptly during the initial stages of the thermal treatment (Figure
5 4d). The saturation magnetization M_s values were obtained by fitting M - H curves to a discrete form
6 of the Langevin function (Eq. S12, ESI). Firstly, M_s increased from 225 to 325 kA/m during the
7 first 24 h of the treatment then it dropped as the treatment was prolonged to 48 h (Figure 4e). As
8 is the case for the ferrimagnetic Fe_3O_4 , the overall magnetization originates from the
9 uncompensated Fe^{2+} spins, therefore the reduced M_s of the IO23/48 can be presumably attributed
10 to the Fe^{2+} deficiencies. Although it seems that M_s reaches an apex after 24 h treatment, the
11 particle's magnetic moment m grows twice (from $5.3 \times 10^{-19} \text{ A} \cdot \text{m}^2$ to $1.1 \times 10^{-18} \text{ A} \cdot \text{m}^2$) upon 48 h
12 treatment. This can be qualitatively discerned by observing that the normalized M - H curves reach
13 the non-linear regime at lower magnetic fields (Figure S12). It is worth to mention that the
14 intermediate IO23/6 nanocubes reveal the most bulk-like Fe_3O_4 inherent properties such as the
15 highest K and M_s values among all the samples. The exchange bias field H_E , which was estimated
16 from the FC hysteresis loops at 10 K (Figure S13), drops gradually over time which indicates a
17 slow reduction in the volume of the AFM-FiM interface. It should be noted that H_E does drop to
18 6.5 mT in the IO23/48 sample. Structural defects such as anti-phase boundaries, spin canting, and
19 tiny FeO sub-domains could be accounted for a non-zero H_E .

1 In order to elaborate on the viscosity and clustering independent heating response of the IO23/48
2 once exposed to the cellular environment or after cellular internalization we have designed two
3 experiments. In the first one, the response of the SAR to a progressive internalization/association
4 of the nanoparticles was evaluated. The nanoparticles (50 μL at 4 $\text{g}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{L}$) were added to a pellet of
5 5×10^6 ovarian cancer cells (IGROV-1 cell line), which simulate a small tumor mass, and the
6 calorimetric SAR measurements were carried out at set incubation periods (0, 15, 45, 90 and 180
7 minutes). The heat profile and estimated SAR values indicate that there was no drop in the
8 particles' heating efficiency within the first 180 minutes, albeit a 30% of the initial nanoparticle
9 dose (0.06mg of iron) was found associated to the cell pellet (Figure. 5b and Figure S14(a)). This
10 suggests that the heating capability of the IO23/48 nanocubes remains unchanged when
11 progressively associated or internalized by the cells (see TEM images of the nanoparticles
12 internalization, Figure S15(a)). This significantly differs from what has been reported for
13 viscosity-dependent iron oxide nanocubes or nanospheres of similar sizes when incubated with
14 tumor cells in similar cellular conditions.

1
2 **Figure 5.** (a) Scheme of the adopted strategy for evaluating the heating performance of the IO23/48
3 particles once interacting with IGROV-1 cell pellet. (b) SAR values measured at field frequency
4 and amplitude of 301 kHz and 24 kA/m at different incubation time intervals. (c) Scheme of the
5 intracellular hyperthermia experiment on the IGROV-1 cell pellet and the nanocubes after 48 h of
6 incubation. (d) PrestoBlue viability assays on the cells re-cultured for 24, 48 and 72 h, which were
7 treated with MHT (red bar) and without (w/o) MHT (pink bar). The viability of the treated cells
8 was normalized to control cells (black bar, no nanoparticles and no MHT exposure).
9 In the second experiment, the suitability of the IO23/48 particles, upon the cellular internalization,
10 to induce temperature raise and cellular damage was probed. For this aim, adherent IGROV-1 cells
11 were incubated with the IO23/48 nanocubes (50 μL at 8 $\text{g}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{L}$ in 2 mL of medium) for 48 h to
12 ensure an efficient particle uptake. It was found that a 75% of the administered nanoparticle dose
13 (0.3 mg of iron) was internalized or associated to the cell pellet, as evidenced by TEM studies

1 (Figure S15(b)). The magnetic hyperthermia treatment (MHT) was performed on the cell pellet at
2 the frequency of 182 kHz and field amplitude, which was varied from 40 kA/m at the beginning
3 of the treatment to approximately 28 kA/m once the desired temperature of 47°C was reached
4 (Figure S14(b)). Remarkably, the cell pellet was able to maintain this temperature for 90 minutes.
5 The cytotoxicity PrestoBlue assay, on the cells once re-cultured for 24, 48 and 72 h, shows that
6 the viability of cells that were exposed to MHT was severely compromised (red bar, Figure 5d),
7 while a modest toxicity was exhibited by the cells that were non-exposed to MHT (pink bar, Figure
8 5d). The intracellular organization and typical cytosolic and nuclear structures of the cells appear
9 to collapse completely after the MHT (Figure S15(c)-(d)). These data indicate that the IO23/48
10 particles are effective mediators for the intracellular hyperthermia as they were able to heat up the
11 cells to clinically relevant temperatures for magnetic hyperthermia under biologically safe field
12 conditions.

13 In summary, we have shown that it is not necessary to have stoichiometric and defect-free iron
14 oxide nanoparticles in order to design efficient magnetic nanoparticles for intracellular magnetic
15 hyperthermia. On the contrary, we have demonstrated here that one can turn cation deficiencies
16 and structural defects into positive features that enhance the heating. We have identified that the
17 FeO-Fe₃O₄ CS nanocubes transform into the Fe²⁺ deficient Fe₃O₄ nanocubes with structural
18 defects *e.g.* anti-phase boundaries and tiny FeO sub-domains, as was revealed by HADDF-STEM,
19 EELS, and ⁵⁷Fe Mössbauer analyses, after 48 h of thermal treatment at 80°C in water. Not only
20 did their magnetic heating (SAR value) increase significantly throughout the process, but the
21 treated nanocubes also exhibit an exceptionally stable SAR regardless of the medium viscosity,
22 aggregation as well as association and internalization to the IGROV-1 cells. The same features
23 have not yet been reported for similarly sized single phase magnetite nanocubes, as they relax via

1 the Brownian process and thus responding dramatically to such environmental stimuli. The
2 nanocubes treated for 48 h have the largest SAR that has been reported thus far for iron oxide
3 nanoparticles in such an environment. We have identified that the survival and migration of the
4 FeO sub-domains, which are randomly distributed throughout the entire particle, are caused by the
5 high pressure exerted by the growing Fe₃O₄ domains. It is plausible that the Fe²⁺ deficiencies and
6 structural defects break the long-range magnetic ordering in the magnetite phase, resulting in
7 reduced H_A and KV_m quantities. These features together with spin canting seem to account for the
8 domination of the Néel relaxation in the IO23/48 nanocubes, which is not a general feature of
9 particles with large magnetic losses at moderate field conditions (*i.e.* 182 kHz and 28 kA/m). These
10 features favor the preservation of magnetic heating under the cellular and intracellular
11 environments.

12 Last but not least, the non-interactive nature and colloidal stability of the freshly prepared CS
13 nanocubes make them very attractive in terms of conducting a particle water phase transfer using
14 any type of water transfer protocol instead of highly interacting single phase magnetic nanocubes
15 (especially those with edge lengths above 20 nm). The processed nanocubes possess a remarkably
16 small anisotropy field H_A given their comparatively small K . Therefore, they would require a
17 relatively low excitation magnetic field in order to go through the major hysteresis loop wherein
18 their full heating capacity will be harnessed. Given that *in-vivo* magnetic particle imaging (MPI)
19 and intracellular magnetic hyperthermia share similar physics of magnetism wherein optimal
20 nanoparticles should relax *via* the Néel mechanism, the engineered 23 nm are potential theranostic
21 agents for combined MPI/MH intracellular assays.

22

23

1 ASSOCIATED CONTENT

2 **Supporting Information**

3 Materials, syntheses, characterization methods, data analyses, numerical simulations, and Figures
4 S1-S15 are presented.

5
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15 **Author Contributions**

16 A.L. and T.P. devised the research. A.L. performed the particle synthesis experiments. A.L. and
17 M.C. conducted the calorimetric hyperthermia measurements. T.B.M. designed and synthesized
18 the polymeric ligands. A.L. and T.B.M. carried out the particle water transfer and DLS analyses.
19 A.L. and H.R. performed the ACS measurements. A.L. analyzed and modeled the ACS results. F.
20 L. gave insight into the interpretation and modeling of the ACS spectra. D.C., L.M., and F.J.T.
21 carried out dynamic hysteresis measurements and data analyses. F.J.L. and E.S. carried out

1 Mössbauer measurements and modeling. F.J.L. and E.S. wrote the Mössbauer section of the
2 manuscript. N.W. and S.B. performed HAADF-STEM and EELS measurements and analyses, and
3 wrote the related sections. L.M. gave insight into the structural and crystallographic features of the
4 particles. A.L. performed all SQUID measurements, analyses, and modeling. S.F. conducted AC
5 mode SQUID measurements. S.M. and A.L. performed the XRD measurements. A.L. analyzed
6 and modeled the XRD patterns. M.C. performed the cellular hyperthermia experiments and wrote
7 the related sections. M.C. performed TEM studies on the cells. A.L. and T.P. wrote the manuscript.
8 All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

9 **Notes**

10 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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1 Table of contents entry

After heat treatment

2 Before heat treatment

Viscosity & aggregation independent SAR behavior

After heat treatment

Before heat treatment